

Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注

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The Wang Bi 王弼 edition and commentaries to the Daodejing 道德經 represent, together with the Heshang Gong 河上公 edition, the most circulated editions of the text. Wang Bi, styled as Fusi 輔嗣, was born in Luoyang in 226 AD and died at the age of 23 in 249 AD, because of an epidemic. A promising philosopher already since a very young age, during the Three Kingdoms period (San guo 三國, 220 – 280 AD), he served as a bureaucrat in the state of Cao Wei 曹魏. Identified by scholarship as either Xuanxue 玄學 (with Lao-Zhuang 老莊 and Huang-Lao 黃老 influences) or primarily Confucian, he is mostly known for his commentaries on the Lunyu 論語 (of which we only have transmitted quotations), on the Yijing 易經, and on the Daodejing: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注 (Commentary to the Laozi) and the Laozi Zhilüe 老子指略 (Introduction to the Laozi). Wang Bi's edition of the Laozi 老子, which accompanies his commentary, is widely regarded as the standard edition of the text, despite showing some later interpolations. Nevertheless, his recension of the Laozi and the attached commentary have been translated into several languages, as well as having influenced the philosophical debate in China for nearly two millennia. The earliest transmitted copies of Wang Bi's edition of the Laozi with his commentary that have come down to us are dated to the Ming Dynasty 明朝 (1368–1644) and some discrepancies are noticeable between the Laozi edition attached to the commentary and the quotations given in the commentary itself. There is a total of 79 passages in which Wang Bi's commentary differs from Wang Bi's Laozi. In 78 of these occurrences, the reading in the commentary matches the reading found in Guodian 郭店, Mawangdui 馬王堆, and other manuscript-editions of the Laozi or in quotations from the Laozi in various earlier texts (e.g., in the Huainanzi 淮南子 or the Zhanguo ce 戰國策). It is plausible that the verses quoted in the commentary represent the Laozi known to Wang Bi, while the Laozi edition attached to Wang Bi's commentary might have suffered more than the commentary from later interpolations and changes (especially elements taken from Heshang Gong's text). The differences between quotations from Wang Bi's commentary in other texts and the transmitted version of his commentary are small, implying that it must be close to the original written by Wang Bi. Wang Bi refers to a Laozi text divided into zhang 章 and pian 篇, but without ever mentioning a division into a Dejing section and a Daojing section. In the Laozi Zhilüe, Wang Bi always refers to the Laozi, while he never calls the text "Daodejing." His philosophical analysis of the Daodejing is based on the centrality of the notion of wu 無 (non-being, nothingness) as the point of origin for the generation of the ten thousand things (wanwu 萬物). Wu, according to Wang Bi, corresponds to the Dao 道 (Way), and this concept is echoed by various metaphors in the body of the text (for example, the hub of a wheel, the valley, the door). Wang Bi also identifies wu with the function of the Dao and of Ziran 自然 (naturalness) meaning that the Dao acts out of nothing, and never acts out of something – it acts with no consciousness. And the sage does the same: he embodies wuwei 無為, not in the sense of "non-action," but rather in the sense of "non-deliberate action." Acting against the principle of wuwei, that is, against the Dao, inevitably brings danger. The sage, albeit being a human being and being involved in human affairs, according to Wang Bi, always acts naturally and responds to things spontaneously and with no personal desires. Wang Bi identifies Confucius with the Laozian sage, capable of wuwei, embodying the principle of nothingness. Wang reads the Laozi asserting that you 有 (being) comes from wu, and that wu is the ultimate substance of being, conferring enormous centrality to emptiness (xu 虛) and to the idea of emptying one's heart-mind in order to respond to things in their ziran. Because of this peculiar understanding of the concept of

emptiness in the Laozi, Wang Bi's commentary played a crucial role in the popularization of Mahayana Buddhist doctrines in China. Wang Bi's provides comments on the various zhang trying to reduce ambivalence in more obscure passages through references to passages of clearer content; he explains the words, clarifies the metaphors, and provides grammatical explications where needed. Wang Bi's Laozi has been transmitted divided into 81 zhang of which two (zhang 31 and zhang 66) are not provided with a commentary. For the remaining 79 zhang, 403 commentary statements are provided in total. It is plausible that the entire comment for each zhang was originally written at the end of the zhang, justifying the presence of repeated verses from the Laozi in the commentary, preceded by 故曰/故/故云/故謂.

Date Range: 200 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Early and early imperial China

Region tags: Asia, China, East Asia

Core area of early and early imperial China

Status of Readership:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Xiong 熊, Tiejie 鐵基, and Chen 陳 Hongxing 紅星, eds. Laozi Jicheng 老子集成. Vol.1-15 . Beijing: Zongjiao wenhua, 2011.
- Source 2: Lou 樓, Yulie 宇烈, ed. Wang Bi Ji Jiaoshi 王弼集校釋. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1980.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/dao-de-jing>
- Source 1 Description: 道德經 ctext

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/dao-de-jing>
- Source 1 Description: 道德經 ctext

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

– Specify: The Wang Bi's edition and commentary on the Laozi are inked on paper. However, we do not have the original text, but later editions.

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is considered part of the so-called "Daoist Canon" of reference for Religious

Daoism (Daojiao 道教).

↳ Is there a culture of oral recitation?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is believed that the Daodejing, or at least part of the text, was conceived for being memorized and orally recited and transmitted, based on its rhymed structure. I. Robinet 1977 also pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas.

↳ Is there a story associated with the origins of scripture?

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god?

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Inspired by high god?

– No

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being?

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings?

– Yes

Notes: The authorship of the Daodejing is attributed to Laozi 老子 (Old Master), a semi-legendary figure whom classical historiography, beginning with Sima Qian's 司馬遷 Shiji 史記, dates back to the 6th century BCE. His biography is shrouded in legend: a contemporary of Confucius and a native of Chu 楚, Li 李 by surname, Er 耳 by given name, he allegedly served as archivist to the Zhou 周. As early as the early imperial period, with the mixing of native and Indian elements, a process of deification of the master began, which passed through the mythologizing of his biography: a legend was spawned concerning his miraculous birth, which occurred when he was already old and therefore wise, based on the very ambiguity of the name Laozi (old master/old child).

↳ Originated from non-divine human being?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is the oeuvre ascribed to Laozi 老子. Wang Bi's view of Laozi is that of a mortal - human - sage who is nevertheless able to teach the concept of wu 無

(nothingness) and the practice of non-purposeful/non-deliberate action (wuwei 無為).

↳ Are the scriptures alterable?

– Yes

Notes: There are several editions of the Daodejing with sometimes significant variations in content, vocabulary, order of passages, and sections. It needs to be noted that the edition of the Daodejing preserved together with Wang Bi's commentary sometimes differs from the passages quoted in Wang Bi's commentary itself.

↳ Do the practitioners generally consider the scripture open to alteration?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting scriptures?

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing has been handed down through a philosophical-literary tradition. Various editions come with an appended commentary, as in the case of the Wang Bi edition and the Heshang Gong edition. In addition, several manuscript editions have been unearthed from ancient tombs. Since the Daodejing is also a benchmark for practitioners of the Daoist religious cult, these people also contributed to its transmission.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures?

– Yes

↳ Can the canon be altered or added to?

– Yes

↳ Are additional commentaries part of the canon as it is currently understood?

– Yes

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing itself is not written in a sacred or religious language, but both the rhymed structure and the expressive complexity of the text, both linguistically and in terms of content, affect the book's mysticism.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Field doesn't know

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1977 pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas. Regarding Wang Bi's commentary, Wagner notes that one of the reasons behind the repetition of some verses from the Laozi at the end of the commentaries for some of the zhang might be an attempt at helping the reader memorize the passages.

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Notes: I. Robinet 1977 pointed out that the poetic form of the text suggests that it was believed that the text could acquire an incantatory force through rhythmic repetition of formulas.

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?
 - Specify: Starting at the beginning of the first millennium CE, the Daodejing has been taken as a reference text for the religious cults and ritual practices associated with Religious Daoism.
- ↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ How often do the rituals take place?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?
 - Field doesn't know

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: In addition to the Daodejing edition accompanied by Wang Bi's commentary, there are several other editions of the text, either handed down from the philosophical-literary tradition (e.g. the edition commented by Heshang Gong), or unearthed manuscript editions (as in the case of the two texts of Mawangdui, or the partial edition in three scrolls found in Guodian). Furthermore, even the quotations in Wang Bi's commentary often reveal discrepancies from the Laozi attached to his commentary, fueling the hypothesis that the commentary was based on a different edition of the Laozi.

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The Daodejing did not originate as part of a collection of texts, but became part of the "Daoist Canon."

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Philosophical

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the previous

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Notes: Neither the Laozi nor Wang Bi's commentary outline a precise distinction between spirit and body.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– Yes

Notes: Chapter 31 deals with war-avoidance and the ritual ceremonies for the deceased in the battlefield. Yet, Zhang 31 does not carry Wang Bi's commentary.

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions both shen 神 (as well as shenming 神明 and shenling 神靈) and gui 鬼.

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Have other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger
 - Yes
 - Notes: The text refers to a sacrifice to the gods, the Tailao 太牢, in which cattle, pigs, and sheep are offered.
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature
 - Specify: Neither the text nor Wang Bi's commentary provide precise information about these

spirits.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: Not specified.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: None.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: Neither the Daodejing nor Wang Bi's commentary on the text guide divination practices. Yet, some scholars, such as S. Allan, believe that the text refers to the use of the shipan 式盤 (a divinatory instrument displaying a schematized version of the cosmos).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: The sage person (聖人) is that person who is able to be free from desires and act in a non-purposeful way, embodying the ideal of wuwei 無為, in the sense of “non-purposeful action” rather than “non-action” or “absence of action.”

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Present & clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts

– Yes

Notes: Acting according to the principle of wuwei 無為 (non-purposeful action) entails always acting naturally and responding to things spontaneously and with no personal desires. This means acting in accordance with the Dao 道 (Way), that, according to Wang Bi, stands as the ontological basis for the existence of the ten thousand things (wanwu 萬物).

↳ Moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities

– Yes

Notes: Acting according to the principle of wuwei 無為 (non-purposeful action) entails always acting naturally and responding to things spontaneously and with no personal desires. This means acting in accordance with the Dao 道 (Way), that, according to Wang Bi, stands as the ontological basis for the existence of the ten thousand things (wanwu 萬物).

↳ Linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma)

– Yes

Notes: Acting according to the principle of wuwei 無為 (non-purposeful action) entails always acting naturally and responding to things spontaneously and with no personal desires. This means acting in accordance with the Dao 道 (Way), that, according to Wang Bi, stands as the ontological basis for the existence of the ten thousand things (wanwu 萬物).

↳ Linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no (sic: have no?) special connection to the metaphysical

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Notes: The text does not address its readers through fictive kinship terminology, but the word mu 母 (mother) is employed in reference to the Dao 道 itself.

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: The book does not focus on the topic of welfare, yet some zhang indirectly refer to the welfare of the people, in particular to the problem of the scarcity of livelihood. E.g., zhang 75.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Education in China has been primarily restricted to males for centuries.

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The Daodejing is explicit in condemning military action and war. The concept of wuwei 無為 (non-purposeful action) is consistently employed to justify the avoidance of war on the part of the sage ruler.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

- ↳ Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?
– No

Food Production

- Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?
– No

Bibliography

General References

- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Wagner, Rudolf G. . A Chinese Reading of the Daodejing: Wang Bi's Commentary on the Laozi with Critical Text and Translation. New York: SUNY, 2003.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Chai, David, ed.. Dao Companion to Xuanxue (neo-daoism). Edited by David Chai. Vol. 1. Springer, 2020.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Wagner, Rudolf G.. "The Wang Bi Recension of the <i>laozi</i>" 14 (1989).
<https://doi.org/10.1017/s0362502800002583>.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Wagner, Rudolf G.. The Craft of a Chinese Commentator: Wang Bi on the Laozi. New York: SUNY, 2000.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, "THE ANNOTATED CRITICAL LAOZI: WITH CONTEMPORARY EXPLICATION AND TRADITIONAL COMMENTARY. By Chen Guying. Edited by Paul J. D'ambrosio and Xiao Ouyang. Modern Chinese Philosophy, 19. Leiden and Boston: Brill, 2020. Pp. Xxiv + 463. Hardback, \$166.00." 46, no. 2 (June 2020).
<https://doi.org/10.1111/rsr.14654>.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Lou 樓, Yulie 宇烈, ed.. Wang Bi Ji Jiaoshi 王弼集校釋. Edited by Yulie 宇烈 Lou 樓. Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1980.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Andreini, Attilio. Laozi: Genesi Del "daodejing". Torino: Einaudi, 2004.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Robinet, Isabel. Histoire Du Taoïsme : Des Origines Au Xive Siècle. Paris: Cerf, 1991.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Robinet, Isabelle. Taoism, 1997. <https://books.google.com/books/about/Taoism.html?hl=&id=rigYHnGDsewC>.
- Reference: Wang Bi's 王弼 commentary to the Daodejing 道德經: the Laozi Daodejing zhu 老子道德經注, Allan, Sarah. "The Great One, Water, and the Laozi: New Light from Guodian". T'oung Pao 89, no. 4 (2003): 237-85.